

MUSIC BROADCASTING IN UZBEKISTAN: GENRE STRUCTURE AND PROGRAMMING STRATEGIES OF TELEVISION CHANNELS

Abdurahimova Gulasal Mukhammadaliyeva

Second-year master's student University of Journalism and Mass
Communications of Uzbekistan, Tashkent

E-mail: abdurahimovagulasal41@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18399834>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 25th January 2026

Accepted: 26th January 2026

Online: 27th January 2026

KEYWORDS

*music television broadcasting,
television programs, music airs,
genre models, Uzbek television
broadcasting*

ABSTRACT

The study analyses the approaches to implementing music television broadcasting in Uzbekistan, using the example of two television channels with different genre-specifics: the non-specialised channel Zo'r TV and the specialised music channel FTV. Based on comparative-typological and content analysis, two dominant models are identified and compared. The Zo'r TV channel implements a model where music is integrated into large shows and reality formats, serving as an additional element. The FTV channel adheres to the classic musical-air model centred on music itself: on the continuous rotation of music videos, thematic blocks, and charts, supplemented by separate show projects. The research confirms that the choice of programming strategy is determined by the target audience and the channel's positioning in the media market, demonstrating the diversity of approaches to producing music content in modern Uzbek television.

Music television broadcasting constitutes an important segment of the mass communication system and functions under the direct influence of audience behaviour and the advertising market. Television programming strategies are largely determined by viewership indicators, target audience structure, and patterns of media consumption [1; 2; 6]. Ultimately, the audience's power to select, interpret, and reject content represents the fundamental force that media institutions must accommodate [1, p. 76]. Television channels are capable of producing in-demand content and maintaining their market competitiveness only through a systematic study of consumer needs [5]. A channel that loses its core audience immediately loses revenue. Consequently, from the very outset of their broadcasting, television channels analyse the market segment to identify the audience for whom they intend to produce content. Once this decision is made, they allocate and tailor their content according to the trends, demands, and preferences of that audience. This principle applies to every new channel, regardless of its format or theme [3].

Alongside the traditional rotation of music videos, modern channels increasingly integrate entertainment shows, reality formats, live broadcasts, interviews, and backstage materials. As a result, musical television broadcasting is no longer limited to a single format,

but is realised through diverse genre models that differ in their structural organisation, content priorities, and degree of musical centrality.

This process is also characteristic of the Uzbek television market, where music broadcasting develops within both specialised and non-specialised channels. However, the presence of musical content in a channel's schedule does not automatically determine its programming model.

Within contemporary television studies, music broadcasting is not limited to a single universal format, but is implemented through several stable programming models. Among the most common are two dominant approaches. The first model may be defined as an exclusively musical model, in which music functions as the core content around which the broadcasting structure is built. This model represents the initial form of music television, whose primary function was the transmission of music videos. Early music channels were clip-centred, relying on continuous video rotation, charts, and thematic selections [4].

The second model can be described as an entertainment-music model. Within this approach, music remains an important component of broadcasting; however, it no longer occupies a central structural position. Instead, the primary focus shifts toward entertainment formats — television shows, reality projects, interviews, and backstage materials. Music functions as one of the variety of possible tools which could be used to construct spectacle-oriented content aimed at audience engagement. Both of these models are represented in the programming strategies of Uzbek television channels Zo'r TV and FTV; however, each channel demonstrates a different dominant focus and applies these models in distinct ways.

The non-specialised channel Zo'r TV primarily relies on the entertainment-music model. Its music-related broadcasting is largely structured around large-scale show formats, particularly competitive vocal projects, such as *Artist* and *Ovoz*, *Ovoz Bolalar*, *Ovoz O'smirlar*, and *Ovoz 50+*. At the same time, Zo'r TV still continues to employ elements of the exclusively musical model through structured programme blocks such as *Real Xit* and *Retro Xitlar*. These formats are based on music video rotation and thematic organisation; however, they occupy a secondary position within the channel's overall programming strategy. As a result, music on Zo'r TV serves not as an independent broadcasting core, but as a component integrated into broader entertainment structures.

In contrast, the specialised music channel FTV demonstrates a dominant orientation toward the exclusively musical model. The foundation of its broadcasting schedule consists of themed music blocks and chart programmes, including *Uz Top Chart*, *Turk Top Chart*, *K-POP Chart*, and *Shazam Chart*. These formats organise musical content according to popularity indicators such as rankings, streaming metrics, and digital audience activity. A significant share of airtime is dedicated to continuous music broadcasting formats — *#UZNONSTOP* and *#FKOKTEYL*. This programming strategy positions the music video as the central structural element of the channel. Nevertheless, FTV also incorporates entertainment-music formats into its schedule. Projects such as *X-Factor O'zbekiston* and *Maska* expand the channel's genre palette, though they do not redefine its overall programming orientation.

A comparison of musical project formats further demonstrates the divergence in the channels' approaches. On Zo'r TV, shows such as *Ovoz* and *Artist* primarily focus on talent discovery and competitive performance. The programme *Ovoz*, in particular, employs the

format of blind auditions, where jury members base their decisions solely on vocal performance. This mechanism places musical ability at the centre of the initial evaluation process. In contrast, programmes such as *Artist* and *X-Factor O'zbekiston* involve open auditions, where jury members assess participants visually and vocally from the outset. While these formats share a common competitive genre foundation, differences emerge in the degree of narrative depth. *Ovoz* and *X-Factor* devote significant attention to participant storytelling, incorporating interviews and off-stage footage that present contestants' personal backgrounds and life experiences in order to familiarise viewers with the vocalists. The show *Artist*, although also featuring vocalist introductions and host interaction, provides comparatively limited biographical detail. Information is generally limited to basic data such as name, occupation, and expectations for the project, resulting in a more superficial portrayal of the character.

The show *Maska*, broadcast on FTV, represents a markedly different application of the entertainment-music model. In this format, music is shifted to a secondary position, while the central dramatic element is the guessing process conducted by the jury. Participants perform in elaborate costumes that conceal their identities, and the programme's primary focus lies in speculation, discussion, and entertainment dialogue among jury members. Musical performance thus becomes part of the spectacle rather than its narrative foundation.

Differences are also evident in the channels' strategies for audience segmentation. Zo'r TV expands its entertainment-music model through age-differentiated versions of the same format, including *Ovoz Bolalar*, *Ovoz O'smirlar*, and *Ovoz 50+*. This approach enables the channel to reach diverse demographic groups by adapting a single entertainment framework to multiple audience categories. FTV applies a similar diversification strategy; however, it does so within the exclusively musical model. Instead of age-specific shows, the channel offers genre-oriented chart programmes such as national, Turkish, K-pop, and digital-platform-based rankings.

A comparison of programming strategies reveals a fundamental genre distinction between the approaches. Modern television channels employ various programme models for music broadcasting, determined by their target audience and positioning strategy within the media market. The Zo'r TV channel implements an entertainment-music model, where music functions as an element of television showmanship and social communication. This is expressed through the use of musical segments within its schedule for vocal reality projects and studio-based formats. In contrast, the FTV channel adheres to a classical music-on-air model, based on a clip-centric broadcasting principle, where charts, thematic music blocks, and continuous video rotation play the key role. The identified distinctions illustrate the differing approaches to music television broadcasting in Uzbekistan, contingent upon the channel's genre structure..

References:

1. McQuail D. *McQuail's Mass Communication Theory*. 6th ed. London: SAGE Publications, 2010.
2. Napoli P. M. *Audience Economics: Media Institutions and the Audience Marketplace*. New York: Columbia University Press, 2003.

3. Dinler A., Atan T., Berberoğlu A. Factors affecting the sustained market position of TV channels: Insights from audience preferences // Sustainability. 2022. Vol. 14, No. 23. Art. 16138.
4. Jones S. MTV: The medium was the message // Critical Studies in Media Communication. 2005. Vol. 22, No. 1. P. 83–88.
5. Rendra W., Widyatama A., Suranto A. W., Mahbob M. H. The determinant factors of television's audience in choosing TV channels in the disruptive era // Profetik: Jurnal Komunikasi. 2021. Vol. 14, No. 2. P. 151–165.
6. Wang Y. Strategies for the future development of television advertising // Highlights in Business, Economics and Management. 2024. Vol. 43. P. 525–534.

